

Effect of Calcination Temperature on Synthesis of g-C₃N₄ and its Application in Photocatalytic degradation of Methylene Blue Dye

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Abstract

In this work, graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄) was synthesized from melamine at different calcination temperatures ranging from 400°C, 450°C, 500°C, 550°C, 600°C, 650°C and 700°C. Structural, morphological, functional and optical properties of synthesized g-C₃N₄ were analyzed by different characterization techniques like XRD, SEM, FT-IR and UV-VIS spectroscopy respectively. XRD results revealed that intensity of peaks increases with increase in the calcination temperature and degree of polymerization increases accordingly. Synthesis of g-C₃N₄ was carried out above 450°C. Diffraction peak observed at 27.6° corresponds to (002) plane at 600°C and corresponding crystalline size is 39.6nm, FWHM is 0.12, d-spacing 3.22 Å, dislocation density is 0.0006nm⁻² and micro strain is 0.0013. SEM images revealed that g-C₃N₄ has stacked sheet like structure. Vibrational bands shown by FT-IR matches to the standard results. As synthesized g-C₃N₄ was used for photocatalytic degradation of methylene blue (MB) dye.

Keywords: g-C₃N₄, calcination temperature, photocatalytic degradation, methylene blue (MB) dye.

Introduction

In recent years, photocatalysis technology is widely used in different applications such as hydrogen storage by water splitting, water purification, in the elimination of organic pollutants, dye degradation [1-3], self-cleaning coatings and high-efficiency solar cell [4].

Methylene blue is an organic dye used in textile, pharmaceuticals and paper industries is highly toxic and non-biodegradable. To overcome this problem photocatalysis approach have been adopted due to its low cost and reliability [5,6]. Now a days, solar radiation driven semiconducting photocatalyst are widely used for the removal of hazardous dye, water contaminant etc. and it became one of the best promising techniques [7]. Many photocatalyst such as TiO_2 [8], BiVO_4 [9], BiWO_6 [10], ZnO [11] etc. have been used for degradation of various organic pollutants. Performance of these semiconducting photocatalyst were good to some extent due to low solar energy absorption, high charge recombination rate, slower degradation mechanism restricts to its practical application of photocatalysis [12].

Wide range of semiconductors Bi based, TiO_2 based, ZnO based, C_3N_4 based materials have been used to degrade organic pollutants such as MB [13], RhB [14], AO [15], Phenol [16], ciprofloxacin [17], tetracycline [18] and so on. Among them, graphitic carbon nitride ($\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$) has received more attention in the area of photocatalysis due to its low cost, medium bandgap(-2.7eV), nontoxic, visible light driven metal free semiconductor having good thermal and chemical stability. Its remarkable applications in the field of waste water treatment, hydrogen evolution, CO_2 reduction [19-21]. $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ can be synthesized from different precursors such as polymerization of urea, cyanamide, dicyanamide, melamine etc. It has limitation in photocatalysis due to low charge separation, low surface area and poor photon absorption above 450nm. Bulk $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ has thickness around 110nm reported. [22-27].

In current work, $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ was synthesized from melamine at different temperatures ranging from 400°C, 450°C, 500°C, 550°C, 600°C, 650°C, 700°C. From various characterization techniques results were tested. Optimally synthesized $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ powder was used for methylene blue (MB) dye degradation using UV lamp. Degradation efficiency of MB dye at certain time interval was studied.

Methodology

Materials

All chemicals were used without any further purification and of analytical grade (AR). Melamine (99%, Sigma Aldrich), De-ionized water obtained from an ultra-water purification system, Methylene Blue Dye solution.

Preparation of sample

Synthesis of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ was done by directly heating melamine in muffle furnace. 10 gm of melamine was taken into crucible covered with lid for different temperatures. Samples were calcined from 400°C to 700°C at the heating rate of 5°C/min for 3 hours. Prepared yellow bulk $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ was ground by using agate mortar to obtain fine uniform powder.

Characterization

X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were obtained on a Rigaku (Japan) X-ray diffractometer with $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.15418 \text{ nm}$). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were obtained on a JSM-6360 scanning electron microscope (JEOL/EO, Japan). Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectra were obtained using IRA-1S WL(ENG230V) SHIMADZU spectrophotometer. The ultraviolet-visible (UV-vis) absorption spectra were recorded on a UV-1800 UV-Vis spectrometer (Shimadzu, Japan).

Photocatalytic test

Photocatalytic activity was carried out by using Xenon lamp of 300 W Xenon arc lamp with an optical filter ($\lambda > 420 \text{ nm}$) as the visible light source, 0.5 gm of optimised $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ at 600°C was dispersed in the 250 ml aqueous solution of Methylene Blue (10 mg/L). The solution was stirred by magnetic stirrer and xenon lamp was fitted above the beaker containing dye solution. Whole assembly was enclosed in wooden box. At certain interval of time, 3.5 mL solution from reaction beaker was collected. Before the light irradiation, the reaction solution was stirred in the dark for 30 min to reach adsorption-desorption equilibrium. The MB concentration was examined by UV-1800

spectrophotometer. Degradation efficiency is given by D (%) as shown below,

$$D (\%) = \frac{C_0 - C_t}{C_0} \times 100$$

where C_0 is the original absorbance value of MB at time $t = 0$ min and C_t is the absorbance value for MB at time t .

Result and Discussion

1. XRD Analysis

Structural investigation of synthesized $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ at different temperatures were analysed by XRD study and shown in fig.1. The scanning range of angle 2θ taken from 20° to 80° . Major diffraction peak observed around 27.6° which corresponds to (002) plane. This shows that distance between the layers of the graphitic material. Results were matched to standard JCPDS card no.87-1526 [24]. For different temperatures ranging from 400°C to 650°C , plane (002) shifted to higher angles (27.08° to 27.8°). Corresponding interplanar stacking distance decreases from 0.328nm to 0.319nm . The $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ gives information about layers of triazine units having 3D A-B stacking organization and it has hexagonal unit cell ($a = b = 4.7420 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 6.7205 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = \beta = 90^\circ$, $\gamma = 120^\circ$) with space group $P\bar{6}m2$ [25]. Crystalline size increases with calcination temperature up to 550°C and there was sudden decrease in crystalline size at 650°C . Crystalline size for temperatures 400°C to 550°C were increased as shown in table (1) and for 600°C it is 39.6nm . Above 650°C sample

started to decompose and crystalline size were obtained 19nm . FWHM was ranging from (0.432, 0.168, 0.192, 0.336, 0.12, 0.14) for temperatures 400°C to 650°C .

XRD analysis leads to conclusion that when calcination temperature increases, intensity of peak increases and it becomes narrower at higher temperatures. Also, the degree of polymerization increases with respect to increase in calcination temperature. Higher calcination temperature leads to denser packing of carbon nitride which forms bulk $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$. Temperature above 650°C , decomposition of carbon nitride took place. At 700°C , no sample remained in crucible, this confirms that excessive thermal heating leads to decomposition of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$. The optimised range of polycondensation was obtained in between 450°C to 600°C .

Figure 1. XRD pattern of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ prepared at different calcination temperatures

Table 1. Calculation from XRD data for various calcination temperature

Sample id	No.	2θ	FWHM	d-spacing [Å]	Crystalline size in nm	Dislocation density nm^{-2}	Micro-Strain
400°C	1	27.0851	0.432	3.28952	15.21	0.004	0.0024
450°C	2	27.7317	0.168	3.21428	22.23	0.002	0.0019
500°C	3	27.1232	0.192	3.28499	24.11	0.001	0.0022
550°C	4	27.4425	0.336	3.24748	47.96	0.0003	0.0014
600°C	5	27.6555	0.12	3.22295	39.6	0.0006	0.0013
650°C	6	27.8798	0.144	3.19753	19	0.0027	0.0032

2. SEM analysis

The morphology of g- C_3N_4 nanoparticles were analysed by using SEM characterization technique. Morphologies at different calcination temperature was shown in fig.2(a-f). The morphologies obtained at 400°C,450°C,500°C shows lumps like structure. Temperature above 550°C images show stacked sheet like morphology.

3. FT-IR Analysis

FT-IR spectroscopy results are shown in the following fig.3 at different calcination temperatures. It gives information about chemical structure of prepared samples at different calcination temperature. For melamine and synthesized g- C_3N_4 , principal absorption band was found in between 1200 cm^{-1} to 1650 cm^{-1} which correspond to the stretching modes of C-N

heterocycles (absorption band at 1205 cm^{-1} ,1230 cm^{-1} , 1319 cm^{-1} ,1405 cm^{-1} ,1546 cm^{-1} and 1624 cm^{-1}). Another characteristic breathing mode of the triazine units around 804 cm^{-1} was observed. The broad bands observed at 3153 cm^{-1} and most of the bands were fall in the range of 3000 cm^{-1} to 3500 cm^{-1} was indicative of N-H stretching vibration modes [4]. Intensity of peak was increased with increase in calcination temperature shows that there is increase in degree of polymerization. At temperature 400°C the characteristic peaks of g- C_3N_4 was not clearly observed that shows that there might be possibility of the formation of melamine intermediate polymerisation could not be completed [23]. The FTIR analysis gives confirmation that the synthesis of g- C_3N_4 obtained above 450°C which is in agreement of previous results of XRD data analysis.

Figure 2. SEM images of g- C_3N_4 prepared at a) 400°C, b) 450°C, c) 500°C, d) 550°C, e) 600°C, f) 650°C

Figure 3. FTIR spectra of pure melamine and synthesized g-C₃N₄ at different calcination temperature

Figure 4. UV-Vis analysis of g-C₃N₄ at different calcination temperature

4. UV-Vis Analysis

Optical properties of g-C₃N₄ were studied by using UV-Vis spectroscopy, the absorption takes place in visible region. Fig.4 shows UV-Vis spectra of g-C₃N₄ at different calcination temperature. Bandgap of g-C₃N₄ was found around 2.7eV [17].

5. Photocatalytic degradation of Methylene Blue

Photodegradation of Methylene Blue dye was carried out using optimised powder of g-C₃N₄ at 600°C. Graph of absorption (a.u) vs wavelength(nm) at different times for dye degradation was shown in Fig.5. The maximum

wavelength was 661.04 Å for which absorption increases for time 0 min to 120 min and dye degradation takes place. By using Beer-Amberts law, degradation efficiency was calculated. Concentration C_t/C₀ vs time in min graph plotted and is shown in Fig.6(a) Degradation efficiency of optimised g-C₃N₄ was achieved up to 51.62%. Graph of ln(C₀/C_t) vs time in min and degradation (%) vs time in min are shown in fig.6(b). and fig.6(c) respectively. Rate constant of reaction was 0.0064097 min⁻¹. g-C₃N₄ had shown good result for photocatalytic dye degradation of methylene blue.

Figure 5. Absorption (a.u) vs wavelength (nm) at different time interval

Figure 6(a). graph of C_t/C_0 vs time (min)

Figure 6(b). Graph of $\ln(C_t/C_0)$ vs time (min)

Figure 6(c). Graph of Degradation (%) vs time (min)

Conclusions

In summary, synthesis of g-C₃N₄ from melamine was carried out at different calcination temperatures from 400°C to 650°C. At 700°C sample was decomposed due to high temperature. XRD study revealed that intensity of peak increase with increase in calcination temperature and becomes narrower at highest temperature also polymerization increases with calcination temperature. It was observed that optimised sample was found at 600°C. FTIR study gave information about chemical group present in the sample. There were stretching modes of C-N heterocycles in principal band range 1200 cm⁻¹ to 1650 cm⁻¹ and the broad bands observed in the range of 3000 cm⁻¹ to 3500 cm⁻¹ was indicative of N-H stretching vibration modes. The characteristic breathing mode of the triazine units was found around 804 cm⁻¹. Optical study was carried out using UV-Vis spectroscopy. SEM images shows the stacked sheet like morphology. As temperature increases polymerisation also increases and bulk g-C₃N₄ was prepared. Optimised g-C₃N₄ was used for methylene blue dye degradation. Reaction rate was found to be 0.0064097 min⁻¹ and degradation efficiency was 51.62% obtained. So that we can use g-C₃N₄ for different applications of photocatalytic degradation of dyes and organic pollutants.

Conflicts of interest: The authors stated that no conflicts of interest.

References

- Gustav Plesch, Michal Gorbár, Ulrich F. Vogt, Karol Jesenák, Melinda Vargová, reticulated macroporous ceramic foam supported TiO₂ for photocatalytic applications, *Materials Letters* 63 (2009) 461–463
- Daisuke Yamasita, Tsuyoshi Takata, Michikazu Hara, Junko N. Kondo, Kazunari Domen, Recent progress of visible-light-driven heterogeneous photocatalysts for overall water splitting, *Solid State Ionics* 172 (2004) 591 – 595
- Soheil Asadzadeh-Khaneghah, Aziz Habibi-Yangjeh, g-C₃N₄/carbon dot-based nanocomposites serve as efficacious photocatalysts for environmental purification and energy generation: A review, *Journal of Cleaner Production* 276 (2020) 12431
- S. C. Yan, Z. S. Li, and Z. G. Zou, Photodegradation Performance of g-C₃N₄ Fabricated by Directly Heating Melamine, *Langmuir* 2009, 25(17), 10397–10401
- Huan Liu, Dongqi Yu, Tianbiao Sun, Hongyun Du, Wentao Jiang, Yaseen Muhammad, Lei Huang, Fabrication of Surface Alkalinized g-C₃N₄ and TiO₂ Composite for the Synergistic Adsorption-Photocatalytic, *Applied Surface Science* 2018 PII S0169-4332(18)33500-1
- Renathung C. Ngullie, Saleh O. Alaswad, Kandasamy Bhuvanawari, Paramasivam Shanmugam 1, Thangavelu Pazhanivel and Prabhakarn Arunachalam 4, Synthesis and Characterization of Efficient ZnO/g-C₃N₄ Nanocomposites Photocatalyst for Photocatalytic Degradation of Methylene Blue, *Coatings* 2020, 10, 500
- Yuehan Su, Ping Chen, Fengliang Wang, Qianxin Zhang, Tiansheng Chen, Yingfei Wang, Kun Yao, Wenying Lv and Guoguang Liu, Decoration of TiO₂/g-C₃N₄ Z-scheme by carbon dots as a novel photocatalyst with improved visible-light photocatalytic performance for the degradation of enrofloxacin, *RSC Adv.*, 2017, 7, 34096–34103
- XU Shoubin, JIANG Long, YANG Haigang, SONG Yuanqing, DAN Yi, Structure and Photocatalytic Activity of Polythiophene/TiO₂ Composite Particles Prepared by Photoinduced Polymerization, *Chin. J. Catal.*, 2011, 32: 536–545
- Jiayang Sun, Yaping Guo, Yan Wang, Di Cao, Shichao Tian, Ke Xiao, Ran Mao, Xu Zhao, H₂O₂ assisted photoelectrocatalytic degradation of diclofenac sodium at g-C₃N₄ /BiVO₄ photoanode under visible light irradiation, *Chemical Engineering Journal* 2017 PII S1385-8947(17)31541-3
- Zaiyong Jiang, Xizhuang Liang, Hailong Zheng, Yuanyuan Liu, Zeyan Wang, Peng Wang, Xiaoyang Zhang, Xiaoyan Qin, Ying Dai, Myung-Hwan Whangbo, Baibiao Huang, Photocatalytic reduction of CO₂ to methanol by three-dimensional hollow structures of Bi₂WO₆ quantum dots, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental* 2017 PII S0926-3373(17)30663-X
- Pragati Fageria, Roshan Nazir, Subhashis Gangopadhyay, Harish C. Barshilia, and Surojit Pande, Graphitic-carbon nitride support for the synthesis of shape-dependent ZnO and their application in visible light photocatalyst, DOI: 10.1039/C5RA12463H
- Yanyan Zhao, Xuhua Liang, Huanxian Shi, Yongbo Wang, Yingkun Ren, Enzhou Liu, Xu Zhang, Jun Fan, Xiaoyun Hu, Photocatalytic activity enhanced by synergistic effects of nano-silver and ZnSe quantum dots co-loaded with bulk g-C₃N₄ for Ceftriaxone sodium

- degradation in aquatic environment, Chemical Engineering Journal 2018 PII S1385-8947(18)31351-2
13. Yangqing Hea, Zhanying Ma, Lucas Binnah Junior, Distinctive binary g-C₃N₄ /MoS₂ heterojunctions with highly efficient ultrasonic catalytic degradation for levofloxacin and methylene blue, Ceramics International, doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2020.01.287
 14. Jie Jin, Qian Liang, Chaoying Ding, Zhongyu Li, Song Xu, Simultaneous synthesis-immobilization of Ag nanoparticles functionalized 2D g-C₃N₄ nanosheets with improved photocatalytic activity, Journal of Alloys and Compounds 691 (2017) 763e771
 15. Simin Matloubi Aghdam, Mohammad Haghghi, Somaiyeh Allahyari, Leila Yosef, Precipitation Dispersion of Various Ratios of BiOI/BiOCl Nanocomposite over g-C₃N₄ for Promoted Visible Light Nanophotocatalyst Used in Removal of Acid Orange 7 from Water, Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A: Chemistry PII: S1010-6030(16)31136-4
 16. Haojie Lu, Qiang Hao, Tong Chen, Linghua Zhang, Daimei Chen, Chao Ma, Wenqing Yao, Yongfa Zhu, A high-performance Bi₂O₃/Bi₂SiO₅ p-n heterojunction photocatalyst induced by phase transition of Bi₂O₃, Applied Catalysis B: Environmental PII S0926-3373(18)30501-0
 17. Xiaojiao Yu, Jie Zhang, Jian Zhang, Jinfen Niu , Jie Zhao , Yuchen Wei , Binghua Yao, Photocatalytic degradation of ciprofloxacin using Zn-doped Cu₂O particles: Analysis of degradation pathways and intermediates, Chemical Engineering Journal 374 (2019) 316–327
 18. Sangeeta Adhikari, Hong H. Lee, Do-Heyoung Kim, Efficient visible-light induced electron-transfer in z-scheme MoO₃/Ag/C₃N₄ for excellent photocatalytic removal of antibiotics of both ofloxacin and tetracycline, doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2019.123504
 19. Bui The Huy, Chu Thi Bich Thao, Van-Duong Dao, Nguyen Thi Kim Phuong, and Yong-Ill Lee, A Mixed-Metal Oxides/Graphitic Carbon Nitride: High Visible Light Photocatalytic Activity for Efficient Mineralization of Rhodamine B, Adv.Mater. Interfaces 2017, 1700128
 20. Noor Izzati Md Rosli, Sze-Mun Lam, Jin-Chung Sin, Abdul Rahman Mohamed, In situ acid fabrication of g-C₃N₄ photocatalyst with improved adsorptive and photocatalytic properties, Materials Letters PII S0167-577X(19)31622-2
 21. Xue Lin, Chang Liu, Jingbo Wang, Shuang Yang, Junyou Shi, Yuanzhi Hong, Graphitic carbon nitride quantum dots and nitrogen-doped carbon quantum dots co-decorated with BiVO₄ microspheres: A ternary heterostructure photocatalyst for water purification, Separation and Purification Technology 226 (2019) 117–127
 22. Sai Zhang, Pengcheng Gu, Ran Ma, Chunting Luo, Tao Wena, Guixia Zhao, Wencai Cheng, Xiangke Wang, Recent developments in fabrication and structure regulation of visible-light-driven g-C₃N₄ -based photocatalysts towards water purification: A critical review, doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2018.09.013
 23. Devina Rattan Paul, Rishabh Sharma, S. P. Nehra and Anshu Sharma, Effect of calcination temperature, pH and catalyst loading on photodegradation efficiency of urea derived graphitic carbon nitride towards methylene blue dye solution, RSC Adv., 2019, 9, 15381
 24. Jing Yang, Huihui Chen, Junhua Gao, Tingting Yan, Fengya Zhou, Shihai Cui , Wentao Bi , Synthesis of Fe₃O₄/g-C₃N₄ nanocomposites and their application in the photodegradation of 2,4,6-trichlorophenol under visible light, Materials Letters 164 (2016) 183-189
 25. Federica Fina, Samantha K. Callear, George M. Carins, and John T S Irvine, Structural investigation of graphitic carbon nitride via XRD and Neutron Diffraction, Chem. Mater., DOI: 10.1021/acs.chemmater.5b00411
 26. David M. Teter and Russell J. Hemley, Low-Compressibility Carbon Nitrides, SCIENCE VOL. 271 5 JANUARY 1996
 27. Yuanzhi Hong, Changsheng Li, Di Li, Zhenyuan Fang, Bifu Luo, Xu Yan, Hongqiang Shen, Baodong Mao, Weidong Shi, precisely tunable thickness of graphitic carbon nitride nanosheets for visible-light-driven photocatalytic hydrogen evolution, J. Name., 2013, 00, 1-3

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